

International Conference

"EdTech Policy and Leadership"

Hybrid – online & in-person

July 25, 2024, Oxford, UNITED KINGDOM

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i> <i>EdTech and Leadership: Transforming Educational Practices and Shaping the Future of Learning Ecosystems</i>	08.45-09.15
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> <i>EdTech Policy: Navigating the Intersection of Technology and Equity in the Digital Age</i>	09.15-10.45 10.45-11.00
Q & A	
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – EdTech and Leadership: Shaping the Future of Education</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> <i>EdTech and Leadership: Pioneering Transformational Change in Education through Innovation, Strategy, and Digital Empowerment</i>	11.00-11.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i> <i>EdTech and Leadership: Driving Transformational Change in Education through Strategic Innovation, Digital Empowerment, and Visionary Management</i>	11.30-12.00
<i>Session 2 – EdTech and Policy: Shaping the Future of Science</i> <i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i>	

CBM International University USA

Akados Learning UK

9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

Location: Oxford Science, John Eccles House, Oxford, OX4 4GP, United Kingdom